

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ISSUES OF IMPROVING TERRITORIAL INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

This article discusses and draws conclusion based on the research of the Investment Program, investment projects and their sources of financing in modern conditions, the features of the formation of financing sources.

Keywords: *investments, regional investments, investment projects, gross domestic product, territorial distribution of investments, investor, investment activity, investment financing, investment share, investment activity, investment attractiveness.*

Introduction

The level of complexity of socio-economic problems in the country depends on the level of the regions development. In sustainably developed regions, revenues to the local budget will be well formed, and local governments will be able to fully fulfill their responsibilities. This is not subject to the central state budget. If the level of development of the regions is low, they, on the contrary, will become a burden for the central state budget. In this regard, the implementation of investment projects in the regions will largely depend on the investment potential of the regions.¹ The investment potential of regions is determined by their investment attractiveness. There will be a decent inflow in investments if the investment attractiveness of the region is high.

Methods and materials

The article examines the scientific works of economists from Uzbekistan and abroad on investment activities, the formation of state investment policy, the implementation of investment projects, and the analysis of sources of financial support for investment relations. The methods of comparative literature analysis, logical and structural analysis, grouping and comparative com-

parison, economic and statistical analysis, and hypothesis substantiation were used as the research methodology.

Results

Although the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities"² provides for investment incentives and financing of investments through the issuance of investment loans, this provision is not reflected in the tax legislation. Therefore, the increase in investment using this financial resource is limited.

However, the effectiveness of this practice is known from foreign experience. The growth of investment resources will have a positive impact on the increase in the production capacity of the regions and will positively solve the problem of employment.

This issue is one of the most pressing issues of strategic importance for the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially in the context of a transition economy. Because the results of our research show that according to the data of 2020, in the territorial structure of investments, they are unevenly distributed between the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (Table 1)³.

Table 1

Regional investment analysis for 2015-2020 years
(in percentages)

Regions	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	The average amount over the years 2015 - 2020	Changes over the years 2015-2020 (+) and (-)
The Republic of Uzbekistan	100,0	100,0						
The Republic of Karakalpakstan	4,7	5,2	10,7	9,4	5,2	3,0	6,4	-1,7
Andijan	4,1	3,5	3,1	4,2	3,6	3,4	3,7	-0,7
Bukhara	8,2	8,4	12,4	8,9	19,5	13,1	11,8	+4,9
Jizzakh	2,4	2,4	1,8	2,2	1,8	2,4	2,2	+0,0

¹ "Strategy of actions on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017. T: Collection of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan", February 13, 2017.

² The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" was adopted on December 25, 2019. <http://www.lex.uz> (system of normative legal acts).

³ Data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.stat.uz).

Regions	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	The average amount over the years 2015 - 2020	Changes over the years 2015-2020 (+) and (-)
Kashkadarya	14,4	18,7	15,1	19,2	17,5	10,4	15,9	-4,0
Navoiy	7,2	8,8	7,7	5,4	4,7	10,5	7,4	+3,3
Namangan	3,4	3,5	4,0	3,5	3,8	3,6	3,6	+0,2
Samarkand	6,4	5,8	5,4	4,6	4,4	5,7	5,4	-0,7
Surkhandarya	5,4	5,2	5,3	4,3	4,1	3,8	4,7	-1,6
Sirdarya	1,7	2,0	1,6	1,5	1,7	2,2	1,8	+0,5
Tashkent Region	2,6	8,4	8,8	8,8	10,0	9,4	8,0	+6,8
Fergana	5,1	4,4	4,7	5,7	5,3	6,1	5,2	+1,0
Khorezm	2,7	2,8	2,5	2,0	1,7	2,5	2,4	-0,2
Tashkent City	23,4	20,8	15,6	19,9	16,0	23,1	19,8	-0,3
Undistributed funds	8,3	0,1	1,3	0,4	0,7	0,8	1,9	-7,5

The analysis of the dynamics of investment changes in the regions of the country shows that the regions with the largest investments are Tashkent (19.8%), Kashkadarya region (15.9%) and Bukhara region (11.8%). Based on the analysis of the table data, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Firstly, in the territorial distribution of investments in the country, there was no significant change in the share of investments attracted in regions other than Tashkent. Only in the Tashkent region, for example, in 2020, we will see a sharp increase in the share of investments compared to 2015.

Secondly, the fact that in a given year, the share of regions in investments directed at the national level decreases and increases, mainly due to the placement of large investment objects in a particular region that are of strategic importance in the future.

Thirdly, the attraction of foreign investment largely depends on the geographical location of administrative territories, the level of development of communication facilities, economic and productive potential, and social aspects.

The next, the attitude to attracting foreign investment to a particular region or the assessment of the microenvironment in the regions within the country also has a certain impact.

Finally, the level of skills of local leaders in the field of market relations, the ability to direct domestic resources into the flow of investment, attract foreign investors based on the characteristics of production in the administrative region, search for potential entrepreneurs and encourage them to attract directly related foreign investment.

The legal and political aspects of the investment climate do not play an important role in such an assessment. Because such relations are considered and resolved in a certain order at the national level. As a result of the study, it was concluded that the share of investments in the total volume of all types of investments in the country is divided into the following 4 groups, and it is necessary to assess the level of their investment activity⁴.

Group 1 - more than 15.0% (area with high investment activity);

Group 2 - in the range of 10.1-15.0 percent (region with good investment activity);

Group 3 - in the range of 5.1 - 10.0 percent (area of satisfactory investment activity);

Group 4 - up to 5.0% (area of unsatisfactory investment activity).

Table 2
The amount of investments in fixed assets per capita in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2015-2020, million soums.

Regions	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Fixed capital investments	44810	51232	72155	124231	195927	202000
Population	31	31.5	32.5	32.7	33.4	34.6
Per capita	1445	1626	2220	3800	5870	5838

⁴ Tuxliev B.K. Issues of improving the system of investments and their financing: Monograph. "Innovative development publishing house", -T., 2021. p 141.

If we place the territories of our country in terms of the level of investment activity in the above-mentioned range of groups, we will witness the following situation. That is, in this regard, it is worth to say separately that the assessment of the activity of investments by regions, taking into account not only their share in the total attracted investments, but also the number of enterprises established and operating in a particular region with the participation of foreign investment, as well as the impact of foreign investment, in our opinion, In this regard, it is worthwhile, first of all, to analyze the growth rate and dynamics of changes in foreign investments and loans by Regions (Table 3).

Analyzing the dynamics of changes in investments and loans in the regions of our country, we can include Tashkent (30.6% of the total volume of investments in

2015-2020), Bukhara region (21.3%) and Kashkadarya region (17.8%) among the regions that have mastered the most investments.

Hence, the evidence suggests that there is a proportional relationship between the share of regions in the total attracted investments and the number of enterprises operating with foreign investment. This level of dependence is influenced by factors related to the investment environment and attractiveness. Although the regulations on the regulation and promotion of investment activities in the country are the same for all regions, the investment attractiveness of the regions is different. Therefore, the factors that affect the attractiveness of investment, in our opinion, will be a subjective factor, that is, it depends on the managerial ability of the leaders of the region.

Table 3⁵

Dynamics of changes in foreign investments and credit resources by regions in 2015-2020, %

Regions	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	The average amount over the years 2015 - 2020
The Republic of Uzbekistan	100,0						
The Republic of Karakalpakstan	5,1	6,1	4,3	1,6	2,7	1,4	3,5
Andijan	3,7	2,5	1,5	3,4	0,3	1,7	2,2
Bukhara	4,1	3,8	30,7	11,7	46,9	30,8	21,3
Jizzakh	0,7	1,9	0,7	1,1	0,5	0,7	0,9
Kashkadarya	7,9	17,7	17,9	31,7	20,2	11,5	17,8
Navoiy	7,8	0,8	9,0	2,9	0,5	9,9	5,2
Namangan	1,9	1,7	1,0	2,6	0,5	0,8	1,4
Samarkand	5,2	4,0	2,0	2,2	1,3	0,9	2,6
Surkhandarya	1,6	1,7	2,4	5,0	1,5	1,4	2,3
Sirdarya	1,4	2,3	1,0	0,6	0,8	0,9	1,2
Tashkent Region	8,1	6,3	3,6	3,4	4,0	5,7	5,2
Fergana	2,4	3,1	2,5	4,9	3,3	3,5	3,3
Khorezm	1,4	4,6	1,7	0,8	0,3	0,9	1,6
Tashkent City	45,7	43,7	21,7	28,1	15,8	28,8	30,6
Undistributed funds	3,0	-	-	-	1,4	3,4	1,8

It is credible to argue that, in assessing the investment activity of the regions, it is expedient to assess not only their size, but also the amount of investment per capita, the level of employment, growth of export potential, the state of reinvestment. Because the amount of investment alone cannot fully represent the investment activity of the region.

Discussion

In the context of a pandemic, a sharp decline in production and consumption in large countries, disruption of global production chains and trade links, large-scale investment to revive the economy due to falling commodity prices in global financial markets lead to higher inflation and higher unemployment. This

situation affects GDP, which can lead to a monthly decline in GDP of up to 2 percent.⁶

Indeed, the pandemic has had its consequences for the economy of Uzbekistan. Given the sharp decline in production and consumption in major economies, disruption of global production chains and trade relations, falling commodity prices in global financial markets, and deteriorating conditions, Uzbekistan's economy, which is part of the global economy, will be softened. . Anti-crisis Fund (10 trillion soums) was created to take effective preventive measures.⁷

Economic activity in developed countries is expected to decline by 7%, and in developing countries- by 3%. This year, production in the European region

⁵ Data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan (www.stat.uz).

⁶ Chakraborty I., Maity P. COVID-19 outbreak: Migration, effects on society, global environment and prevention. International Journal Science of the Total Environment 728 (2020) 138882. www.elsevier.com/locate/scitotenv

⁷ COVID-19 pandemic and the fight against the global economic crisis: Center for Development Strategy, www.strategy.uz

could fall by up to 10 percent, while countries such as the United States and Japan could lose up to 6.1 percent of their gross domestic product. The economy is expected to contract by an average of 4.7 percent in Eastern Europe and Central Asia and 6 percent in Russia.⁸

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) predicts that the negative effects of the pandemic could lead to a 40 percent reduction in foreign direct investment worldwide by 2020-2021. This is the lowest figure in the last 20 years.⁹

Investment attractiveness depends on a system of criteria that attracts investors to direct their funds to this area. It can be observed in the economic literature that the groups of factors that affect the investment attractiveness of regions are different. For example, the factors influencing the investment activity of the regions were studied objectively and subjectively by V.M.Askinadzi and V.T.Maksimova¹⁰, A.N.Asaula, N.I.Pasyad change rapidly and slowly, K.V. Baldin, on the other hand, has both positive and negative influences.

Porter rejects the conclusion that international trade and foreign investment have only a positive effect on the country's economy. He argues that international trade and foreign investment may have a negative impact on the economies of some countries, that is, they may hinder the growth of production efficiency.

Interpretation of results on investment activities of the regions in our country are regulated by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities". Local public authorities within their competence and in the field of state regulation of investments and investment activities:

- implementation of investment policy at the local level to stimulate the expansion of investment in the relevant territory of the country, including attracting investment, further improving the investment climate in the region, supporting the development of enterprises in the region;
- study and identify promising projects that require investment, as well as free state facilities and land plots, taking into account the needs and potential of the regions (resource, natural and climatic, labor, etc.);
- consideration of issues directly related to the activities of investors, as well as, if necessary, proposals for the implementation of promising business initiatives and projects by attracting direct investment;
- identify factors that hinder the timely and effective implementation of investment projects in the region, including investment projects with foreign investment, and take prompt measures to eliminate them;
- improving the efficiency of the use of investments in the region's economy

⁸ Eminov A. Pandemic and post-pandemic period: how is the investment policy in foreign countries? Employee of the Legal Policy Research Institute under the Ministry of Justice
⁹ Nasirov E. I. The impact of the crisis caused by the coronavirus pandemic on the world economy. Electronic

based on the analysis of the activities of enterprises with foreign investments, as well as the fulfillment of investment obligations by investors;

- development of proposals for the improvement and diversification of investment cooperation with foreign banks, funds, agencies and companies in the region on a mutually beneficial basis;
- implement measures to attract foreign investment to create more favorable conditions.

Conclusions and suggestions

As a result of the study, the following conclusions were made on the topic:

1. Socio-economic and natural factors affect the degree of investment in the regions and increase their efficiency. Particular importance is the identification of the most important factor groups that will contribute to the active attraction of foreign investment in the regions and increase their efficiency.

2. The assessment of the impact of foreign direct investment on the economy is not limited by macroeconomic indicators, but also values the impact of investment projects on the socio-economic development of regions, analyzes the activities of enterprises with foreign capital, develops, selects and implements investment projects, and should take into account the effectiveness of large-scale measures.

3. Calculations to identify the main factors that ensure the active attraction of foreign investment in the economy of Uzbekistan and increase the efficiency of their use show that the regions are expanding production infrastructure, developing transport and communications, improving the quality of education, and providing effective employment, bringing the quality of state institutions to a qualitatively new level, liberalizing foreign trade, curbing inflation and improving the tax system are the main factors that stimulate the attraction of foreign investment.

4. In order to actively attract foreign investment to our country and increase the efficiency of its use, it is important that each region uses its relative advantages, untapped potential, growth resources and potential. Because when placing production capacities, the relative advantages of the regions are taken into account, the availability of such factors as available resources, infrastructure, and labor, increase the efficiency of capital use and ultimately ensure the competitiveness of products.

5. Improving the quality of administrative processes, improving the regulatory framework and legislation, developing production infrastructure, including transport and communications, electricity, gas and water supply, labor force as a necessary condition for increasing the efficiency of foreign investment in the regions to increase the inflow of investment and organizing the rational use of labor resources.

scientific journal "International Finance and Accounting". No. 3 June 2020. Page 7.

¹⁰ Askinadzi V.M., Maksimova V.T. Investment business - 2012.

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